

RESEARCH ON COTTON HARVESTING MACHINE SPINDLES-DRIVEN
TENSIONER ROLLER

A.B. Gulmatov, N.I. Menglimuratov

Tashkent State Technical University Faculty of Mechanical Engineering

Correspondence: Mr.akmalgulmatov0609@gmail.com

Annotation. The article analyzes the two-dimensional structure of the coil in the direction of the spindles of the cotton-harvesting machine, is devoted to the study of their shortcomings and advantages, as well as their peculiarities. The proposed ribbon-driven principle scheme is presented on the example of the introduction of constructive calculations.

Keywords. Cotton Machine, belt drive, spring, spindle.

Introduction. In the vertical spindle Cotton Machine (CHM), it is the kinematic and geometrical parameters of spindles that determine its basic agro technical parameters. The most important among the features that provide its kinematic parameters are motion-transmitting lane angles to the spindle. Ribbon extensions should ensure that during the one-time rotation of the spindle drum, the spindle is extended in two different directions of movement. These are the pressure drum on the spindle drum, which is attached to the cotton fibers in the opening of the spindle tooth in the working zone of the spindle to ensure that the cord is wrapped in the body together with the separation zone, it is necessary to rotate in the opposite direction to the initial direction and to allow the wrapped cotton pad to separate from the cord. In order for these processes to be performed as required, friction between the fasteners of the tape and the spindle is required to be in one thread. To ensure it, a tension bracket is installed on one side of the tape drive (Figure 1 A, b).

(Figure 1 a, b). 1 the device of spring assembled position of driving belt drive

(Figure 2). 3 spring devices

In the first picture, in which one common tension coil is placed in the three-band combined circuit presented in the first picture, the straps are mounted separately, and in each of them a separate tension coil is installed. The straps in the one we quoted (figure 1) are tapped using a single coil, which in turn speeds up the bending of the and in (Figure 2), each tape is tapped with a separate coil, and if one of them loses its working capacity, the effect of this on the remaining two-lane extension will be felt, but the working position will be better than that of a single-lane-driven one. Two-lane proceedings were also used in the previous proceedings (SXM-4.8).

Using the dimensions of the coil, which tension the ribbon transmission

$$T = \frac{FD}{2} \cos \alpha \quad \text{va} \quad M_H = \frac{FD}{2} \sin \alpha \quad (1)$$

(1) with the help of a nozzle, we can determine the tensile strength that affects it.

T-torsion torque (N*mm)

F-the direction of the tangent force on the central axis of the tangent (n) (Figure 3).

D-Tangerine medium diameter

α -angle of ascent of the spring ores (usually)

M_n-bending moment (N*mm)

This tensile strength should be at least 1/3 of The found tensile strength F for the tensile strength F on each band of the three-lane tensile strength F (F=45-52 N) by determining the appropriate amount of tensile strength F for the single-lane tensile strength.

(Figure 3). Spring

Using the given, find the torsion and bending moment of the torsion of the torsion for the solution of the bite of the torsion .

$$F=45...52 \text{ N}$$

$$D=18 \text{ mm}$$

$$T = \frac{FD}{2} \cos\alpha = \frac{50 * 18}{2} \cos 10 = 443 \text{ Nmm} = 0,443 \text{ Nm}$$

$$M_H = \frac{FD}{2} \sin\alpha = \frac{50 * 18}{2} \sin 10 = 78.14 \text{ Nmm} = 0,78 \text{ Nm}$$

$$c = \frac{D}{d} \Rightarrow d = \frac{D}{c} = \frac{18}{6} = 3 \text{ mm} \quad c = 5 \dots 12 \quad c = 6$$

$$\text{tg}\alpha = \frac{h}{\pi D} \Rightarrow h = \pi D * \text{tg}\alpha = 3.14 * 18 * \text{tg}10 = 9.96 \text{ mm}$$

Using the given, we find the diameters of the spring for the three-spring proceedings.

$$F=45...52 \text{ N}$$

$$T=148 \text{ Nmm}=148 \text{ Nm}$$

$$D = \frac{2T}{F \cos \alpha} = \frac{2 * 148}{50 * \cos 10} = 6.01 \text{ mm} = 0,006 \text{ m}$$

$$c = \frac{D}{d} \Rightarrow d = \frac{D}{c} = \frac{6.01}{6} = 1 \text{ mm} \quad c = 5 \dots 12 \quad c = 6$$

$$tg \alpha = \frac{h}{\pi D} \Rightarrow h = \pi D * tg \alpha = 3.14 * 6.01 * tg 10 = 3,32 \text{ mm}$$

c-spring indexes

Conclusion. As a result of analyzing and comparing the spindles' angles in the two different constructions mentioned above, a court with three different types of spindles on the degree of reliability is preferable, however, in a single-spindle procedure, the spindle rollers may have more time to be ingested on account of the overlapping portion in the input section. But there is a high probability that as a result of the loss of working capacity of a single porcine, a whole proceedings will come to an unfit state.

References:

1. Решетов Д. Н. Детали машин: Учебник для студентов машиностроительных и механических специальностей вузов.— 4-е изд., перераб. и доп.— М.: Машиностроение, 1989.— 496 с.: ил.
2. Ш.Равутов , А.Кодиралиев (ТашГТУ).Об одном способе повышения эффективности применения приводов шпинделей хлопкоуборочной машины.
3. Хлопкоуборочная машина МХ-2,4. Технические условия Ts 25272604-027:2017. АО «ТЗСХТ», 2017. 22-31 бетлар.
4. Сабликов В.М. Хлопкоуборочные машины.—М.: Агропромиздат, 1985.— 152 с.